

The Study of Tourism Development In Tamil Nadu With Special Reference To Nilgiris District

Dr. Prince Paulantony.K¹, Nivetha.V²

^{1,2} Dept of B Com (Professional Accounting)

^{1,2} Sri Ramakrishna College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Abstract- Tourism is significant for fulfilment of the many economies round the world. The number of jobs created by tourism in many various areas. Tourism is one of the main sources of country's revenue. Nilgiris is a mountain range and it has its attractions of mountain areas, tea plantation, beautiful forests, rivers, sightseeing. In recent days tourism has reduced in Nilgiris due to Covid protocols. It is one of the major summer tourist spots among Tamil Nadu. The objectives are to seek out and develop the necessities in the tourist places, accommodation, public areas, etc., and to evaluate the tourist's opinion on the event of tourism in Nilgiris District. The Nilgiris district is also known as Blue Mountains. It is a large area of mountains which spread over the borders of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala. The design used is descriptive method. The questionnaire are collected through convenient sampling. This study involves responses of 103 respondents on tourism development in Tamil Nadu with special reference to Nilgiris district.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism means spending time pleasantly and relaxingly away from home. Tourism is one of the main sources of country's revenue. Country's economic income has increased through tourism income and revenue. Some amount of share capital has been subscribed by the State government. The objective of the tourism corporation is providing infrastructure facilities of transport and accommodation to the tourists. Tourism is one of the world's fastest growing industries as well as major source of foreign exchange earnings and employment for developing countries. Tamil Nadu has the biggest tourism industry in India which has percentage of 21.31% of domestic and 21.86% of foreign tourists. Our state rank second place in domestic tourist visits are 494.8 million and ranks the highest which is numbered 6.86 million for tourism in the country.

Tamil Nadu is well known for temple towns hills stations, waterfalls, national parks and natural environments. According to WTO tourism defines "beyond the common perception of tourism as being limited to holiday activity only." There is a great opportunity for foreigners to learn about new culture through tourism. Moreover, local members

also experience benefits in their own country. The one of the fastest growing tourism is Mountain tourism. Tourism development was incorporated during July 1971 under The Companies Act 1956. Nilgiris is a mountain range and it has its attractions of mountain areas, tea plantation, beautiful forests, rivers, sightseeing. The tourist spots are Ooty, Coonoor, Mudumalai National Park, Botanical Garden, Pykara Waterfalls, Doddabetta Peak. The Nilgiris is well known for Eucalyptus oil and tea. In recent days tourism has reduced in Nilgiris due to Covid protocols. It is one of the major summer tourist spots among Tamil Nadu.

OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the infrastructure to develop and upgrade the tourism value in Nilgiris District.
2. To seek out and develop the necessities in the tourist places, accommodation, public areas, etc.,
3. To evaluate the tourist's opinion on the event of tourism in Nilgiris District.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The important element in tourism development is attraction because they're the stimulating force for tourism. For the development of tourism in Nilgiris, adequate support facilities should be provided to energize the visitors. The valuable experience of visitors depends on the availability of tourist development facilities and their importance in education, shopping, lodging, art and crafts etc., The infrastructure of tourism development in Nilgiris and development in tourism potentials had hardly been searched so far. The development tourism is not very successful. The competition and creativity in advertising campaign is the most crucial issue in developing tourism. The important reason for non-development is tourism are problem with uncleanliness of public areas, waste disposal, lack of travel guide, lack of transport facilities and residence within tourist place.

Having understood the study and also the state of problem. The researchers should find the need of study and final output. The presentation of "The Study on The Role of Tourism Development of Tamil Nadu with Special Reference

to Nilgiris District.” The items what should be developed in tourism of Nilgiris are collecting responses from visitors.

- What should be develop and upgrade the tourism value in Nilgiris District?
- What must be develop the necessities in the tourist places, accommodation, public areas?
- What is the tourist’s opinion on the event of tourism in Nilgiris District?

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Smith (1977) opines mountain communities are specific and unique in their cultural exhibits and used for tourism cause nowadays, especially performance of nonsecular interests, historical events, ceremonies are in great demand for monetary benefits brings commercialization and cheapening of values, traditions and customs. More negative impacts are perceived by local people thanks to the commercialization approach like increased land encroachments, overcrowding vandalism, inflation, increased alcoholism, crime, prostitution, gambling and property boom etc affects the wellbeing of the community and reduces the moral standards of the host population.

Karanti and Mishra [2010] in his book “Promoting Tourism in India – A Case Study”, stated that the potential for development of tourism at a given destination depends the most amount on the provisions of a robust tourism resource base, as on the tourist plant facilities in terms of accessibility, internal transportation, accommodation, recreation and entertainment provisions, agency and tour operation services, shopping opportunities and then on.

Uma Krishna [2010] in her article “Travel and Tourism – A Service Marketing Perspective” identified that folks within the travel and tourism industry-travel agents, tourist guides, hotel and restaurant staff, transport personnel, etc., played a really important role in brand building and delivering customer satisfaction.

Saravana and Joseph [2011] in their study “Cultural Tourism in Kerala: A Study with Special Reference to Malabar” attempted to review the role of presidency in promoting cultural tourism in Kerala. They inferred that the most purpose of visit of the domestic and foreign tourists to Malabar has been identified as pleasure. Foreigners stay longer days than domestic travellers their family as they were on a day trip.

Vivek Sharma [2015], Integrating Pilgrimage and Rural Tourism for Rural Development – A case study of Jammu Region. This paper will explore the phenomenon of

pilgrimage tourism in the perspective of Vaishno Devi Shrine to boost the rural tourism in Jammu region. The aim of this study is to determine, how a pilgrimage destination is helping to promote nearby rural tourism centres, and the opportunities, issues, and challenges faced by the tourist and intermediaries. Tourism makes an enormous contribution to local economies through job creation. Tourism in the state has led to the development of the whole service industry including transport.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The area of the study was under Nilgiris district. The Nilgiris district is also known as Blue Mountains. It is a large area of mountains which spread over the borders of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala. Ooty is the headquarters of the Nilgiris. There is no historical evidence is there to prove that the Nilgiris was ruled by ancient kingdom. The research design is based on descriptive research. Its method used to reanalyse the historical events related to tourism development in Nilgiris.

The source data used in this study is primary data and it is gathered through google forms of respondents by using questionnaire methods.

The sampling procedure used in this study was convenient sampling. The target of respondents was who had visited Nilgiris. Questionnaire surveyed with tourist of Tamil Nadu, neighbored state and others. About 103 respondents were responded for analysis.

IV. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table: 1 Background of the respondents

Sno	Variable	Options	Frequency	Percent
1	Age Group	Less than 20	48	46.6
		21-30	32	31.1
		31-40	11	10.7
		41-50	6	5.8
		Above 50	6	5.8
		Total	103	100
2	Gender	Male	58	56.9
		Female	25	24.1
		Total	103	100
3	Qualification	School Level	10	9.7
		Undergraduate	67	65
		Postgraduate	18	17.5
		Professional	5	4.9
		Other (ITI)	3	2.9
		Total	103	100

4	Occupation	Private Employee	19	18.1
		Government Employee	9	8.7
		Self Employed	3	4.9
		Industrialist	2	1.9
		Student	41	59.2
		Other (unemployed)	7	6.8
Total		103	100	
5	Monthly Income	Less than 10000	55	53.4
		10000-20000	16	15.5
		20000-30000	13	11.7
		30000-40000	9	8.7
		More than 40000	11	10.7
Total		103	100	
6	Marital Status	Married	30	29.1
		Unmarried	73	70.9
		Total	103	100

Sl no	Variable	Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
1	Prefer to stay	Private hotels	66	64.1
		Government cottage	3	4.9
		Walkin's house	15	14.6
		Classified hotels	17	16.4
		Total	101	100
2	Satisfaction level of housekeeping	Satisfied	38	36.9
		Neutral	46	44.7
		Not satisfied	19	18.4
		Total	103	100
3	Satisfaction of cleanliness of rooms	Satisfied	33	32
		Neutral	49	47.6
		Not satisfied	21	20.4
		Total	103	100
4	Satisfaction of quality of foods	Satisfied	38	36.9
		Neutral	49	47.6
		Not satisfied	19	18.4
		Total	106	100
5	Satisfaction of services of house-keepers	Satisfied	41	39.8
		Neutral	36	35
		Not satisfied	26	25.2
		Total	103	100
6	Good quality of foods	Satisfied	38	36.9
		Neutral	49	47.7
		Not Satisfied	22	21.4
		Total	109	100
7	Satisfied with the accommodation	Satisfied	38	36.9
		Neutral	42	40.8

8	Roads are strongly constructed	Not Satisfied	21	22.3
		Total	103	100
		Strongly disagree	16	15.5
		Disagree	20	19.4
		Neutral	39	37.9
		Agree	22	21.4
Total		68	65.8	
Total		103	100	
9	Promotes social interactions among tourists	Strongly disagree	10	9.8
		Disagree	24	23.3
		Neutral	41	39.8
		Agree	22	21.3
		Strongly Agree	6	5.8
		Total	103	100
10	Tourism increases pollution, noise etc.	Strongly disagree	8	7.8
		Disagree	22	21.4
		Neutral	40	38.8
		Agree	23	22.3
		Strongly Agree	5	4.9
		Total	103	100
11	Tourism improves public services	Strongly disagree	13	12.6
		Disagree	14	13.7
		Neutral	33	34
		Agree	31	30
		Strongly Agree	10	9.7
		Total	101	100
12	Tourism deteriorates the natural environment	Strongly Agree	13	12.6
		Disagree	20	19.4
		Neutral	33	34
		Agree	22	21.3
		Strongly Agree	12	11.7
		Total	101	100

From the table 2, it is found that the majority of the respondents 64.1% used to stay in private hotels. 35% of the respondents says that knowledge level of tourist was fourth level. 44.7% are neutral in satisfaction of housekeeping. 47.6% are neutral in cleanliness of rooms. 39.8% are satisfied with services of housekeepers. 47.6% are neutral in quality of foods. 39.8% are neutrally satisfied with accommodation. 37.8% are neutral with roads are constructed, 39.8% respondents are neutral in Promoting social interactions among tourists, 38.8% are neutral in Tourism increases pollution, noise etc., 34% are neutral with Tourism improves public services. 34% are neutral with Tourism deteriorates the natural environment.

V. FINDINGS

From the above table, it is inferred that

- Majority 46.6% of the respondents are in the age group of Less than 20.
- 63.1% of the respondents are female.
- 65% of the respondents are Undergraduate.
- 59.2% of the respondents are Student.
- 53.4% of the respondents are less than 10000.
- 70.9% of the respondents are unmarried.

- 70.9% of the respondents got information through friends and family.
- 33% of the respondents visited Nilgiris first time.
- 60.2% of the respondents visited occasionally.
- 56.3% of the respondents stayed for 2 or 3 days.
- 64.1% of the respondents in private hotels.

VI. SUGGESTION

- To arrange a tourist guide for the new visitors to explore the tourist places.
- To reduce some extinct cost of the accommodation and entry fees for the tourist during seasonal times or vacation.
- To improve more transportation to visit the tourist places.

VII. CONCLUSION

Travel and tourism have been growing's rapidly across the globe. It gives several positive impacts on tourism development such foreign exchange earnings, employment, economic development etc., Othe side negative impacts such as overcrowding, over pollution, parking problem, deforestation etc., The tourism industry in Tamil Nadu has developed by leaps and bounds due to the unique environmental and scenic beauty of the locale it has been blessed. Its social and political climate have been very impressive. The ever-growing tourism industry has made some changes to it through Tamil Nadu has a weak track record as far as industrial growth is concerned.

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